

A Multidisciplinary Approach to Policing: Strategies for Effectively Dealing with Crime in the Transition Toward an Ideal Policing Model

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Abstract:- The purpose of the article was to distinguish between policing frameworks, policing systems, policing strategies, and policing models. It also analyzed the current policing and resource strategies in use so that readers could make an informed choice about what should guide an ideal policing model. The goal was to determine the needs and inadequacies in the current policing system and to offer suggestions for what should guide the SAPS's ideal policing model. Exploration, evaluation, and comprehension of the data gathered during the study process would help to achieve this. Literature, study participants in their respective policing, security systems, and institutions, as well as the state of the policing system at the time, would all be sources.

The prevalent "fire brigade" or "reactive" techniques of policing are criticized and replaced with community policing, problem-oriented policing, and intelligence-led policing. In the latter, the police respond individually to problems as they arise and resolve them there and then. They leave after that and wait for the next critical incident. Response policing lacks any sense of strategy. There aren't any long-term goals. Beyond surviving in the present, there is no goal. Police reform that will give it more direction is a goal shared by community policing, problem-oriented policing, and intelligence-led police. They offer substitute models.

The field of information analysis is becoming more and more important for assisting in the provision of policing services. An emphasis on minimizing harm and managing risk, combined with meeting demand, are important motivations. The demand for information to be accessible, processed, where necessary shared, and understood is influenced by a greater emphasis on access to information about policing issues and police force performance as part of a more community-focused approach, statutory changes that further support partnership working, and the development of shared outcomes and targets, such as Local Area Agreements. Along with structural and policy changes that have an impact on how police forces are organized, evaluated, and the organizations they must work with, a more complex criminal environment and an evolving technological infrastructure have an impact on the data that can be

gathered, stored, and cross-referenced. Crime analysis has found its niche in this confluence of data availability, inter-agency cooperation, risk minimization, and the very real need to draw connections in order to comprehend both the environment of crime and policing responses. However, it is unavoidable that the process of analysis and the analyst who does the assignment would face tremendous expectations and pressure as a result of being driven by such a wide range of demands. Police employ these analytical techniques to create plans for reducing and preventing crime. The procedure has a rating promising and contributed to a large drop in crime and disturbance.

Keywords:- Community Policing, Intelligence Led Policing, Crime Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

As criminals discover and invent new methods of committing crimes, policing faces significant obstacles worldwide. The police and social scientists should create new policing philosophies or models that will address the needs of policing in the twenty-first century in order to prevent and combat crime. A proactive rather than a reactive approach to policing is what the police should adopt in order to achieve progress in crime prevention. Modern police techniques are necessary due to the altering nature of communities as well as the crime and violence that afflict these communities. Strategies that were successful in the past may not be so today. The volume, nature, and shifting nature of communities force the police to look for more efficient ways to deter and combat crime.

The police need to adopt progressive measures in response to changes in crime and terrorist tactics. The terrorist acts serve as a wake-up call to the police and the intelligence community about the capabilities of criminals in the United States and elsewhere in the world. Peterson (2005: 1) highlighted four important lessons that should be taken away from the tragic 11 September 2001 terrorist assault in the United States of America. The first is that gathering intelligence is everyone's responsibility; the second is that a culture of intelligence and collaboration is necessary to protect the United States from all forms of crime and threats; the third is that for intelligence to be successful, it must support the entire operation of the law

enforcement agency; and the fourth is that crime prevention and deterrence should be based on the collection and analysis of information from all sources.

A policing model is a method of policing that is based on a certain policing system and is guided by a particular policing framework. It is a systematic, future-focused, and targeted approach to fighting crime that aims to create a unified national standard of policing that can adapt to and take into account the varied geographic layout and demographic diversity in the nation. Community, traditional, democratic, and many other kinds of policing are illustrative examples. A policing model aims to standardize policing methodology by guiding policing strategies, approaches, organizational design, infrastructure, culture, and operational processes. It is larger and more thorough than a plan and implicitly considers the strategy's effectiveness as well as its capacity to be implemented. Community, traditional, and democratic police models, among many others, are examples of policing strategies (Weisburd & Eck, 2004).

II. THE POLICE'S POLICING APPROACHES, INITIATIVES, AND STRATEGIES

The police used a number of tactics and interdepartmental strategies to improve its policing competence in an effort to fulfill its duty of preventing, investigating, and combating crime, upholding law and order, and protecting Republic people. The next section goes into further information about these tactics, programs, and approaches:

➤ Sector Policing

As a national police program that followed the community policing strategy outlined in the SAPS Act, 1995, Sector Policing was established in South Africa in 2003. It is mostly based on the country's version of Neighbourhood Policing. (Maroga, 2003). The goals of sector policing are listed in National Instruction 3 of 2013 as follows:

- Stronger ties between the police department and the neighborhood;
- Collaborate closely with the neighborhood;
- Increase communication between the police department and the community;
- Form a partnership with the neighborhood;
- Make it possible for the police to comprehend neighborhood issues by locating and resolving their root causes;
- Bolster public confidence in the police; and
- Provide a high-caliber service with the assistance of the neighborhood;

The ability to successfully identify crime hot spots and their underlying causes is one of the benefits of sector policing. Additionally, resources are targeted and concentrated in accordance with the needs of each area, making communities easier to administer. Additionally, there is an improvement in community and police

cooperation (Maroga, 2003:14-15). In certain places, sector policing has decreased crime-related anxiety, boosted community satisfaction, and promoted responsibility-sharing for crime prevention (Smith, 2008:55).

- *However, there are a number of difficulties with the program's implementation. (Maroga, 2003:15–16; Smith, 2008:56) cites a few of these:*
 - ✓ The low level of participation in the forums as a result of the SAPS and community members' ignorance of sector policing.
 - ✓ Insufficient attendance and engagement in forums' meetings.
 - ✓ A lack of resources and the idea that sector policing is resource-intensive.
 - ✓ Lack of sector commander training regarding effective sector management and how to involve other role players.
 - ✓ Sector overload at large stations makes it challenging for management to keep an eye on employees and assure responsibility.
 - ✓ Police officers' unwillingness to do their part.
 - ✓ Insufficient cooperation between the sectors.

III. INTELLIGENCE-LED POLICING

In truth, it is falsely attributed to a large number of distinct "crime-fighting" operations that rely on the work of analysts and intelligence experts using "crime mapping," "crime pattern analysis," "data analysis," and other "problem-solving" techniques. (Ratcliffe, 2002). Another component of intelligence-led policing (ILP) also employs analysts and other specialists, but in this case, the emphasis is on identifying groups or individuals using covert tactics with the aim of arresting them or taking other action to prevent them from committing new offenses (Peterson, 2005).

Ratcliffe and Guidetti (2006) and Budharm (2015: 50) define intelligence-led policing as "an information-organising process that allows policing agencies to better understand their crime problems, thereby enabling them to make informed decisions on how to best approach specific crime challenges." The South African Police Service has a Crime Intelligence Division that makes it easier to execute intelligence-led police by acquiring, compiling, and analyzing crime information to produce policing that is actionable (South African Police Service, 2008: 126). A former member of the SAPS, Major General (Dr.) De Kock, however, stated that "crime intelligence or crime information should underlie all crime combating activities of the police" while offering expert testimony at the Khayelitsha Commission (Commission of Inquiry into allegations of police inefficiency in Khayelitsha and a breakdown in relations between the community and the police in Khayelitsha) (Khayelitsha Commission Report, 2012). De Kock (Khayelitsha Commission Report, 2012), in support of this assertion, claimed that intelligence-led policing will help the police respond to the following five inquiries:

- What crime is being committed?
- Where and when is it taking place?
- What motivated the crime's timing and location?
- How was the crime committed?
- Who committed the crime, and why?

The Audit Commission was essential in finding the "best value" among public sector companies. In its seminal report on ILP, *Helping with Enquiries: Tackling Crime Effectively* (Audit Commission, 1993), it questioned the effectiveness of the traditional reactive model at the time. It advocated a crime-reduction strategy based on intelligence that concentrated scarce operational resources on the criminal rather than the offense. There was a significant shift in the discussion about policing after the study's publication. The Home Office and the police department were both greatly impacted by the findings.

According to Reiner (2000: 217), there are enough examples of this type of creative policing that have undergone thorough analysis to imply that targeted policing techniques can be successful in reducing crime and the fear of crime in a "significant, if modest" way. Although "academics and the informed public" were enthusiastic about ILP strategies, Skogan (2008: 23), who questioned the scope of ILP, noted that for policymakers and police leaders "the political risks involved are considerable, and efforts to change the police frequently fall far short or fail." ILP was only an addition to pre-existing systems, according to Gill (2000), who questioned whether it truly represented a fundamental shift in contemporary policing.

IV. NEIGHBORHOOD POLICING, CRIME REDUCTION, AND COMMUNITY POLICING

Community policing builds on a dedication to POP and relies on "decentralization and a reorientation of patro" in order to foster greater engagement and communication between the people and the police (Skogan and Hartnett, 2005: 428). Community policing, in theory, is dedicated to collaboration, problem-solving, and meeting the requirements of communities. (Skogan and Hartnett, 2005). Requests for the police to collaborate more closely with the communities they serviced in the 1970s, according to Tilley (2003a).

In 1977, John Alderson, Chief Constable of Devon and Cornwall, made the first well-known plea for a British policing structure that was better suited to the needs of citizens. Others, like Kenneth Newman, the Metropolitan Police Commissioner from 1982 to 1987, were eager to accept Alderson's challenge. In British policing, community policing strategies are now widespread, and many of the multi-agency problem-solving methods they have produced are consistent with the proactive, preventative policing methods that Newman (and those who came after him, like Imbert and Condon), as well as others, had advocated. Alderson's ideas, however, markedly diverged from the majority, authoritarian position in British policing in the 1970s, as evidenced by James Anderton, the Chief Constable of the Greater Manchester Police, who

vehemently advocated for the continuation of the status quo in terms of crime control (Savage, 2007) for further analysis).

Initiatives for crime reduction in collaboration with communities and crime prevention have both been linked to community policing. The Scarman Inquiry (1981) led to the creation of the first official police/community partnerships, the Police Community Liaison Groups, and many Home Office announcements and research papers supported further partnership growth. Most analysts concur that the Morgan Report (Standing Conference on Crime Prevention) 1991 was the most important development in this context. Morgan argued that municipal governments should participate in crime prevention efforts because they have extensive control over matters such as housing, education, and planning that "all have an effect on the manifestation of criminal tendencies and their development" (Byrne and Pease, 2003: 293).

The Crime and Disorder Act of 1998 considerably improved community policing and crime reduction in Britain (CDA). The Act made it a legal requirement for chief constables and local governments to develop a strategy to based on a neighborhood crime audit, reduce crime. These tactics transformed into the neighborhood policing initiative that chief officers are currently pursuing in Britain. According to Tilley (2003), the best way to understand neighborhood policing in Britain is as an effort to combine the essential components of POP and ILP. A new dimension was brought to the conversation by Innes' description of "signal crimes" as incidents that "act as warning to people about threats to their security and that have a disproportionate impact on the way people, think, feel, or act."

V. PROBLEM-ORIENTED POLICING (POP)

Another proactive strategy that the British police agency allegedly adopted during this time was POP. According to common belief, Goldstein (1979) invented the POP aesthetic in the USA, and his concepts propagated throughout the industrialized world. According to Newburn (2003: 387), no one has had more of an effect than Goldstein on the shift in policing toward problem-solving, and his work over the past 30 years "has spawned a variety of cognate policing models" in addition to having an impact on practical.

According to Goldstein (1979), raising the level of service provided to communities was unlikely to result from continuing to place a focus on strengthening the police organization, which was evident in policing throughout the Western world at the time. Instead, the police should adopt a commitment to a more methodical procedure for looking into the origins and reasons of those problems in order to limit the number of problems that came to their attention to a manageable level (within the department's existing resources). This would require more precise problem definitions, information gathering from both internal and

external sources, and an overall wider search for answers than has hitherto been done (Eck and Spelman, 1987).

Police departments should expand on current crime prevention programs to investigate several other potential solutions to each policing issue. (Goldstein, 1979). These essentially consisted of investigating physical or technological changes in the social environment (situational crime prevention measures), advocating for adjustments in the delivery of government services, disseminating trustworthy crime prevention guidance, fostering new abilities among police officers (such as providing additional training in conflict resolution or providing more advanced first-aid training), and enacting new forms of authority (such as the right to issue "official" warnings in pubs).

POP is often implemented in Britain using a standardized set of technologies for analysis and environmental scanning. The SARA technique, which involves sequentially doing environmental scanning, intelligence analysis, response, and assessment, has been favored by British analysts. According to Tilley (2003: 321), the actual process is significantly "messier" and involves a lot more overlap than the SARA construct would imply. The problem analysis triangle is another tool analysts may utilize (PAT). The PAT is similar to Felson's (1998) routine activity model in that it addresses issues from the perspectives of the victim, the perpetrator, and the environment (Tilley, 2003).

A problem-oriented strategy necessitates more initiative from the police in resolving issues and may also need them to be assertive in developing partnerships with local communities. (Goldstein, 1979: 258). Due to the fact that it wouldn't be perceived as undermining "the prevailing value system," Goldstein thought that the police establishment would accept this. He didn't account for the resistance of the police officers in the trenches, though. The introduction of civilian analysts as "problem solvers" was not always well accepted, the researchers found, and resistance frequently led to the "misuse and exclusion" of analysis from operational responses. (Cope, 2003: 357). This may not come as a revelation given how inadequate and inefficient the conventional intelligence system is. There has also been some societal resistance to POP. According to Read and Tilley (2000), almost every force in Britain professes to participate in POP, but it hasn't proven to be a popular career path for frontline detectives and patrol officers who prefer to take the initiative (Tilley, 2003).

VI. STANDARD MODEL OF POLICING

In the past, dealing with the police was largely a reactive process. In direct response to crimes being committed or crimes being reported by citizens, it places a strong focus on follow-up enforcement, prompt replies to citizen calls to the police, investigations of crime, and the capture of criminals. In the United States, proactive policing is a relatively recent movement that involves police departments using a systematic strategy to deter crime. Because of social unrest, rising crime rates, and growing

doubt about the efficacy of conventional policing strategies, a crisis in public trust in law enforcement first appeared in the 1960s. Innovative police methods and policies that adopted a more pro-active approach started to emerge in response starting in the 1980s and 1990s.

The term "proactive policing" is used in this report to describe all policing tactics that have the prevention or reduction of crime and disorder as one of their goals and that are not reactive in the sense that they don't concentrate primarily on uncovering ongoing crime or on investigating or responding to crimes after they have occurred. Instead of referring to a tactical choice made by police agencies to utilize proactive police responses in a systematic approach to minimize crime, the term "proactive policing" distinguishes it from the daily decisions made by police officers to be proactive in particular situations. In the United States nowadays, proactive policing techniques are frequently employed. They are a collection of concepts that have permeated the policing landscape rather than individual programs implemented by a small number of agencies.

Proactive police examines the data and methodological gaps regarding the following topics: (1) the impact of various proactive police strategies on crime; (2) if they are utilized in a biased manner; (3) whether they are employed in a legal manner; and (4) community response. This research provides a thorough analysis of proactive policing, taking into account not just its effects on crime prevention but also its wider consequences for the justice system and American communities. "Standard model" tactics were mostly created during the reform or professional era, which started around the 1930s, as standard police ways to combating crime (Kelling & Moore, 1988). Even though these strategies date back at least 60 years, they nevertheless form the basis of most police operations today. For a good reason, they are regarded as the "standard model."

Weisburd and Eck (2004: 49) concentrated on five elements of the "standard model," but as the evidence for these three is the weakest, we only address the first three on this page. The fourth and fifth aspects are covered separately on pages under the heading "What do we need to know more about?". Random patrol across all parts of the community:

- Quick response to service requests for emergencies (i.e. 911 calls.)
- Generally speaking, strict enforcement and arrest policies are in place.
- Generalized criminal investigations.
- Expanding the size of police departments.

➤ *What is the Evidence on the "Standard Model" of Policing?*

On our Review of the Research Evidence, under "What doesn't work?" are "Standard model" tactics noted. The data foundation is outlined below, although as Sherman (2013) points out, more research is required to explicitly compare these tactics to more successful ones. As a technique for police to fight crime, random preventive patrol (also known

as random beat patrol) has either little to no proof of success. The Kansas City preventative patrol experiment, carried out by Kelling and colleagues, was the most significant and well-known investigation in this field (1974). The amount of preventive patrol across beats did not appear to have a significant effect on reported victimization, reported crime, or levels of citizen satisfaction, according to their research. The study offered no proof that regular preventive patrols work as a deterrent or as a means of enhancing police efficacy and efficiency.

Based on the literature on hot spots policing, the conclusion that officers randomly monitoring beats is not an effective crime deterrent makes logical. The fact that crime is heavily concentrated in a small number of locations across cities is one of the reasons hot spots policing is a successful tactic. From an efficacy and efficiency perspective, it makes little sense to respond with a strategy based on the random allocation of police resources across vast geographic areas because crime is highly concentrated throughout cities.

Rapid response to 911 calls is a second common policing strategy that doesn't seem to have much of an influence on crime. Rapid reaction, especially in the case of calls for a "hot" robbery or burglary, might occasionally result in the capture of perpetrators. However, there is little proof that prompt response to the majority of calls raises the number of people apprehended or lowers crime (Spelman & Brown, 1984). Citizens frequently wait too long after an incident occurs for quick response to be really helpful, which is the problem. Our point is not that police should disregard 911 calls, but rather that they shouldn't assume that reducing response times to the vast majority of calls will result in an increase in crime control.

Last but not least, increasing arrests all over is not particularly useful in lowering crime. The evidence for the reactive arrest theory, according to Sherman and Eck (2002: 310) "is remarkably unencouraging at both the community and individual levels of analysis," they write. Because there is conflicting evidence regarding interventions that primarily increase arrests and because many of these interventions also include other components, it can be challenging to separate the effects of different factors, it is difficult to draw firm conclusions about the effectiveness of arrest as a crime-control strategy. We find little evidence to suggest that reactive arrest strategies that are more widely implemented will be highly effective in lowering crime, and instead we propose for increased concentration, either.

VII. REVIEW OF POLICING MODELS USED GLOBALLY

➤ *Policing Models*

A policing model is an approach to policing that is founded on a certain policing system and is directed by a specific policing framework. It was created to offer a uniform national standard of police that can accommodate and take into consideration the inequalities in the country's population as well as its varied geographic topography. It is an intentional, planned, and future-focused approach to

battling crime. Various types of police, including neighborhood, conventional, democratic, and many others, are illustrative. A policing model directs policing strategies, techniques, organizational design, infrastructure, culture, and operational processes with the goal of standardizing policing methodology. It is more extensive and comprehensive than a plan and indirectly takes the efficacy and implementability of the strategy into account. Policing tactics include, among many others, community, conventional, and democratic police approaches. (Weisburd & Eck, 2004).

➤ *Traditional Policing Model*

Traditional policing is a reactive model based on Peel's 9 policing principles, which include: preventing crime and disorder through the use of force and severe punishment; a police service that is subject to public approval; adherence to the law by the police in order to earn and maintain public respect and approval; diminished use of force by the police in achieving objectives in order to preserve public favor; Clearly defined roles for the police and the judiciary, the use of minimal physical force when necessary, upholding community relations where the police can be perceived as members of the public, strict adherence to police-executive functions, and the absence of crime and disorder are all indicators of a successful police force (Brown, 2013: 13–14). While on patrol, police officers often stay at their stations and respond to calls for help and crimes. According to the majority of studies, it refers to the method of policing whereby officers wait for calls from the public before responding. Police performance is evaluated based on reaction times, and statistics are used to explain crime. Because it is reactive, traditional policing is incident-driven and heavily dependent on patrols to deter crime. As a result, it does not really address community or societal needs. In order to solve crimes, the police deploy random patrols and quick actions. These policing strategies rely more on deterrence than on prevention (Dempsey and Forst, 2016: 261). The focus is on reacting to calls, and using one's own initiative to stop crime is not taken into consideration.

Despite conducting patrols at random, the police hardly ever engage with the public. Few people in the communities they patrol are familiar to the officers. Traditional policing relies on deterrence and focuses on law enforcement, maintaining the peace, resolving crimes, defending civil liberties, and offering services to the general public. The model disregards societal or communal needs (de Guzman, Das & Das, 2014: 133-134). When David Hunt, South Australia's commissioner of police, writes that "the police force reacted to reported crime in the same way that a fire brigade reacts to a call about a fire: they rushed forth, dealt with reported situation, and then returned to base to wait for the next call," he is describing the reactive nature of traditional policing. (Hunt, 1992: 143). The methods listed by Dempsey and Forst (2016: 261) are some of the ones the police use:

- Unplanned routine patrols that can be conducted on foot, by bicycle, on horseback, or even in a police car;
- Prompt response to citizen requests. refers to the police's response to calls to for emergencies, direct calls to a police station, Visits to community service centers, or approaches to officers on patrol to report a crime in progress;
- Detectives conducting retrospective inquiries into earlier offenses.

➤ *Intelligence-Led Policing Model*

By "collection and analysis of information related to crime and conditions that contribute to crime, resulting in an actionable intelligence product intended to aid law enforcement in developing tactical responses to threats and/or strategic planning related to emerging or changing threats," Carter and Carter (2009: 11) define intelligence-led policing." "Intelligence is nothing but information generated to direct police action," as Cope (2004:190) succinctly put it. That data extends beyond the conventional "secret intelligence," and it may contain hotspots and opportunities for criminal activity, patterns of criminal behavior, and series of crimes (Den Hengst and Ter Mors, 2012). Therefore, depending on the level of operation, an intelligence analyst is not necessary to confine themselves to police databases and file cabinets. Additionally, he or she should research additional governmental and regulatory organizations, personal records, and public sources including media and the internet (Peterson in Smith, 1997: 2). An increase in police workload is one of the main factors influencing the use of intelligence-led policing. As a result, only when police agencies are aware of "how, where, and when to use police resources to combat crime" can successful and efficient policing be carried out (Den Hengst & Ter Mors, 2012).

➤ *Objectives of Intelligence-Led Policing*

It entails the use of criminal intelligence analysis as an objective decision-making tool to promote crime reduction and prevention through efficient policing techniques and external collaboration projects built on an evidence base, as explained by Ratcliffe (2003: 2). The aim of intelligence-led policing is to gather data, produce intelligence on criminal activity and offenders, and use such outputs to guide police actions. The following can be achieved through the use of intelligence-led policing, which focuses on repeat offenders and recurring crime (Archbold, 2018: 54):

- A concentrated or targeted strategy to crime prevention that can help law enforcement find criminals through overt and covert methods;
- Effective handling of trouble spots for crime and disturbance;
- enhanced investigation of connected incidents and crimes; and
- The use of preventative measures, such as collaborating with neighborhood partnerships to lessen crime and unrest.

➤ *Components of Intelligence-Led Policing*

Utilizing intelligence-led by concentrating on both the crime phenomenon and the offenders, policing has historically been employed to minimize crime. Ratcliffe (2003:3) highlights the components of intelligence-led policing that are crucial for the model's successful application using the 3-i model. The 3i model is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Fig 1 Model of the Intelligence-Led Policing Process (Ratcliffe, 2003)

Police departments must first comprehend the criminal environment, which is essentially the setting in which crimes take place. The criminal environment is a constant component of the working environment for police agencies, according to Ratcliffe (2003: 3). It is the physical environment and social circumstances in which crime occurs (Mashiloane, 2014: 182). Therefore, it is necessary to "influence" decisions on crime reduction, preventive, or combat Decision-makers are operational and leadership levels, and it is their duty to use the intelligence gathered to "impact" on the criminal environment, according to Ratcliffe (2003: 4). It is important to have capable systems, people, analytical tools measures by sharing the intelligence with decision-makers. and a shared understanding of how to interpret the criminal environment. It is also important to have passionate and competent decision-makers who can look into strategies to help reduce crime rates (Ratcliffe, 2003: 4).

➤ *Characteristics of Intelligence-Led Policing*

Den Hengst and Ter Mors (2012) identified four characteristics of intelligence-led policing:

- Intelligence-led Information is key to effective policing, and as was previously mentioned, this information goes beyond "secret intelligence." It also extends beyond criminals and crime to encompass things like the human and physical resources employed in crime prevention and eradication.
- Intelligence-led Information analysis is crucial to policing. Depending on the nature of the problem and the desired result, analysis can range from the simplest to the most complex computerized procedure. Peterson asserts that it can be carried out for tactical as well as strategic goals (in Smith 1997: 2). Tactical analysis is carried out at all levels within operational divisions and at the station level in South Africa. The security cluster's many

departments each have a role in strategic analysis, while the NICOC is in charge of coordination.

- Intelligence-led policing focuses on the skills and actions of decision-makers when utilizing analyzed data: Decision makers need to understand the value of analytical products and have the motivation to use them if Intelligence-led Policing is to be successfully implemented. Most importantly, analysts need to have interpersonal abilities that will allow them to influence decision-makers in addition to analytical ability.
- Intelligence-led In order to make decisions regarding how to deploy police resources, decision-makers must employ information and expertise that has been thoroughly analyzed. Because there will never be enough resources, it is essential that decision-makers employ analytical tools to deploy the few available resources wisely in order to maximize their utilization.

➤ *Methods used in Intelligence-Led Policing*

- The organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (2017: 38–39) lists certain ways that can be used to guide decision-making and advance professional knowledge of efficient law enforcement procedures, such as:
 - A general phrase for a variety of analysis types, such as trend identification and hotspot analysis, is "crime pattern analysis;"
 - Demographic/social trend analysis evaluates how socioeconomic and demographic trends, as well as population changes and homelessness, affect criminality;
 - The direction, frequency, and strength of links between associates in a criminal network are evaluated by network analysis;
 - Market profiles analyze the black market for a certain good or service, such narcotics or prostitutes;
 - The business model and methods used by offenders or organized crime groups are determined by their criminal business profiles;
 - Risk/Threat analysis evaluates the severity of dangers or threats that criminals or organizations pose to specific potential victims, law enforcement, and the general public.

Intelligence-led being able to use the information that has been acquired, its analysis, and developed intelligence as the primary tools for proactive and effective policing makes policing a unique model.

➤ *Community Policing Model*

A policing approach known as "community policing" aims to improve links between the police and the communities they serve. It is a philosophy that encourages organizational tactics that back the methodical application of alliances and problem-solving methods to proactively address the immediate circumstances that give rise to public safety issues including crime, social disorder, and fear of crime. (Office of Community Oriented Policing Services, United States Department of Justice, 2014: 1; Virta in Coquilhat, 2008: 18). In order to identify problems, analyze them, and come up with appropriate solutions, community

policing aims to create an active relationship between the police and the local community. The police must make an effort to foster an environment where the community can participate and be willing to collaborate in order to accomplish this goal (Cordner and Biebel Perkins in Coquilhat, 2008: 18).

The focus on strengthening police-community ties in the battle against crime is what makes community policing special. In order to protect the safety of the community, community policing is a policing method that encourages a positive relationship between the police and the community by fostering trust (Cossyleon, 2019: 1). In the fight against crime, a theory known as "community policing" places a focus on the police and the community's relationship and mutual trust. (Straub, 2020). Building solid police-community relationships based on trust is the main goal of community policing (Hart & Salcedo, 2020).

Community policing encourages the police to involve the community in policing, to proactively deal with community concerns (Cooper, 2017). According to Cooper (2017), the police and the community are not supposed to work in isolation. Community policing is used as a tool to build mutual trust between the police and the community (Hart & Salcedo, 2020). The authors further indicated that police-community relations could be improved through community policing. Lebron (2019) argued that although a positive attitude plays a major role in building good police-community relations, it is crucial to have sufficient resources. According to Lebron (2019), this will ensure that the police regularly contact the community. The author further indicated that where the police are expected to do more with insufficient resources, voluntary participation of the community in policing is important.

➤ *Characteristics of Community Policing*

The Buffalo State University of New York (n.d.:2) explains that:

- Community Policing is **service orientated** where the community is considered the "client" and the police as "providers".
- Community Policing is a **partnership** that is based on the objective of determining community needs and policing priorities.
- Community Policing is effective at **problem solving**, an approach which focuses on exploring potential causes of crime.
- Community Policing is an agent of **empowerment** and create a sense of joint responsibility in addressing community concerns.
- Community Policing ensures **accountability** of the police to communities they serve since it provides an opportunity for mechanisms through which the police can be held accountable (e.g. Civilian Oversight).

➤ *Principles of Community Policing*

Community policing is based on the following principles (SEESAC, 2006: 4; Cheurprakobkit, 2002: 713):

- *Philosophy and Organizational Strategy:*

Community policing is both a philosophy (a way of thinking) and an organizational strategy that allows the police and the community to work closely in developing creative ways to solve the problems of crime.

- *Commitment to Community Empowerment:*

Community policing demands that everyone including civilian should take initiatives in translating the philosophy of policing into practice.

- *Decentralized and Personalized Policing:*

The essence of community policing is the creation and development a new breed of police officers who act as a direct link between the police and the community.

- *Policing by Consent, not Coercion.*

- *The Police as Part of the Community, not Apart from it.*

- *Partnership between the Police and the Community:*

The police and community work together to identify and respond to community needs. Other agencies also form part of the partnership to broaden the approach towards crime prevention.

- *Personal Service:*

Community policing ensures that the business of policing.

- *Regulatory Framework For Community Policing*

Mamosebo (2014: 3) mentions that Community Policing in South Africa was influenced by the inability of law enforcement to address serious crime due to the fragmented and unplanned efforts that were employed in the past. After 1994 the government introduced a number of legislative instruments to ensure an integrated and community-based approach to crime prevention and they include the:

- Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 (Act No. 108 of 1996) – Section 41(1);
- White Paper on Safety and Security of 1998;
- National Crime Prevention Strategy of 1996; and
- SAPS Guidelines for the Establishment of Crime Prevention Partnerships.

- *Critical Components of Community Policing*

The Critical Components of Community Policing include (Coquilhat, 2008:14; Office of Community Oriented Policing Services, United States, 2014: 1, 11):

- *Community Partnerships* - between the law enforcement agency and the individuals and organizations they serve to develop solutions to problems and increase trust in police.
- *Organisational Transformation* - the alignment of organisational management, structure, personnel and information systems to support community partnerships and proactive problem solving.
- *Problem Solving* - the process of engaging community in the proactive and systematic examination of identified

problems to develop and evaluate effective responses to solve crime or social disorder that has potential of generating crime. It is the process of scanning an environment to identify and prioritize problems, analyse to understand what is known about the problem, developing solutions to reduce the problem and evaluating the impact of the responses or solutions adopted.

- *Methods of Community Policing*

Some of the methods of community policing include (Buffalo State University of New York, n.d.:2): Patrols; Community consultations whereby police consult citizens in communities to determine policing priorities; Neighborhoods watch groups; Awareness campaigns and Customer satisfaction surveys.

- *Democratic Policing Model*

Haberfield and Gideon (2008:17) describe Democratic Policing as a type of a policing model whereby the police takes accountability for the rule of law and the community. Under this model, the police are expected to:

- Respect the rights and guarantee the security of all citizens in a non-discriminatory manner.
- Enforce laws that have been adopted democratically; and
- Abide by the rule of law and be accepted by the public.

Moreover, in constitutional democracy the police must not be politically aligned, but must focus on protecting democratic political processes and activities. Bruce and Neild (2005:18) in their book, “The police that we want: A handbook for oversight over police in South Africa” argue that police in a constitutional democracy can achieve political impartiality by acting as follows:

- Policing public gatherings and demonstrations in a manner which supports freedom of association and assembly;
- Providing equal protection under the law to individuals and political parties in exercising their political rights;
- Investigating, arresting, and bringing before court members, groups who seek to promote their political end through violence; and
- Not exercising their powers to favour or prejudice individual political interests and causes.

- *Principles of Democratic Policing*

Democratic Policing is based on the following principles (Mlotha, n.d.):

- **Representativeness:** the police must represent the communities they serve.
- **Responsiveness:** the police must be responsive to community needs and expectations.
- **Accountability:** the police must be accountable to the law.
- **Respect for human rights.**
- Giving operational priority to **servicing the needs of individual citizens and private groups.**

➤ *Objectives of Democratic Policing*

The Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (2008: 11) and Mohler (2009) highlight the following as the main objectives of democratic policing are to:

- Maintain public tranquillity and law and order;
- Protect and respect the individual's fundamental rights and freedoms;
- Prevent and combat crime;
- Provide assistance and services to the public;
- Serve the people and society;
- Always behave and perform ethically;
- Adhere to the democratic principles without exceptions;
- Ensure best quality of performance;
- Strive for the utmost transparency when and wherever possible; and ensure accountability.

➤ *Characteristics of Democratic Policing*

Democratic Policing is characterized by police's (Barley in Mlotha, n.d.):

- Adherence to rule of law.
- Subject to continuous monitoring.
- Respect to human rights, especially those that are required for the sort of political activity that is the hallmark of democracy.
- Provision of top operational priority to serving the needs of individual citizens and private groups.

Uniqueness of Democratic Policing places emphasis on adherence to the rule of law, respect for human rights and accountability to the public.

➤ *Components of Democratic Policing*

According to Nalla (2009: 523), the elements of Democratic Policing include:

- The basic function of serving the public by preventing crime and maintaining order;
- A police service which is directly dependent on the public approval of police existence;
- The police seeking public approval but maintaining impartiality in offering services to all groups;
- The police intervening in the lives of citizens, albeit with strict limitations, as provided by the constitution and other legal provisions;
- The police using force to the extent that law is observed and order is restored;
- The police mirroring the socioeconomic, cultural, and other characteristics of the community in which they serve;
- The police functioning as a part of the community they serve rather than separately; and
- Finally, the police held accountable to the public.

➤ *Regulatory Framework for Democratic Policing*

The legislative / policy imperatives that regulate Democratic Policing in South Africa include the:

- Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 (Act No. 108 of 1996);
- South African Police Service Act, 1995 (Act No. 68 of 1995);
- White Paper on Safety and Security of 1998;
- White Paper on Safety and Security of 2016;
- White Paper on Policing of 2016;
- National Crime Prevention Strategy of 1996;
- SAPS Guidelines for the Establishment of Crime Prevention Partnerships; and
- National Development Plan vision 2030 of 2012.

➤ *Human Rights-Based Policing Model*

Human Rights-Based Policing (HRBP) is a model of policing where the police adhere to, and comply with (Philippine National Police, 2013: 25):

- National or domestic laws on human rights related to law enforcement or police functions.
- International human rights principles, standards, and practices related to law enforcement or police functions.
- International treaties, conventions, and protocols related to law enforcement or police functions.

HRBP model advocates respect for human rights and dignity, transparency, accountability, rule of law, and people's active participation in democratic governance and institutionalisation of this model occurs when human rights principles are taught and applied at both operational and administrative functions of the police organisation (Philippine National Police, 2013: 25-26). Human Rights Based Policing exist with its objective to empower claim holders to claim their rights, while strengthening the capacities of police officials to meet their duties and obligations as human rights protectors (Philippine National Police, 2013: 25). HRBP is also a strategic approach for re-orienting the police organization from the traditional policing models or theories based purely on social control or repression to a new paradigm anchored on genuine respect for human rights and dignity, transparency, accountability, rule of law, and people's active participation in democratic governance (Philippine National Police, 2013: 26).

Uniqueness of HRBP model is its emphasis to the need for the police to work in collaboration with human rights organisations nationally and internationally as well as the need for the police to receive training on human rights at recruitment and periodically thereafter (Den Boer, 2011). In South Africa, the model finds support from the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, Act (Act 108 of 1996).

➤ *Principles of Human Rights-Based Policing*

HRBP is based on the following principles (Philippines National Police, 2013: 36-41):

- **Participation:** active involvement of the people in public planning and decision-making.
- **Accountability:** recognition that the purpose for existence of the police is to serve and protect the public.

- *Non-discrimination*: providing police services to all persons without any bias or prejudice.
- *Transparency*: the process of allowing the public to gain access to policies, plans, documents, rules and regulations, and other information that affects their safety, security, and well-being.
- *Human dignity*: as a principle means that the HRBP values the inherent and immutable dignity of every person at all times, without exception.
- *Empowerment*: as principle means that HRBP acknowledges and respects people's capacity to think and act freely and on their own behalf for the purpose of identifying solutions to problems.
- *Rule of law*: as principle HRBP observes the principles and values of justice, equity, fairness, and impartiality in all police policies, plans, decisions, procedures, and all other actions related to law enforcement and public safety.

➤ *Characteristics of the of Human Rights-Based Policing*

HRBP is characterized by (Philippines National Police, 2013: 27-32):

- Strict observance of police policies and operational procedures.
- Adherence to national/domestic and international laws, treaties, standards, and protocols on human rights.
- Professional competence and courteous service.
- Respect for rule of law and civilian supremacy.
- Pro-democracy and pro-citizen.

➤ *Components of Human Rights-Based Policing*

The critical components of HRBP are (Philippines National Police, 2013:32):

- **Respect for human rights**: Refraining from interfering with the enjoyment of people's rights in the ambit of the law.
- **Protection of human rights**: Implementing laws that provide equal protection to all persons from human rights violations by state authorities or by non-state actors.
- **Fulfillment of human rights**: Established organisation which implements systems, mechanisms or procedures that enable people to claim and enjoy their rights.

➤ *Methods of Human Rights-Based Policing*

The Human Rights Policing model implies that the police should adopt a comprehensive human rights policy which incorporates international human rights standards in its internal directives, human rights training for the police at recruitment and cooperation with national and international human rights organisations (Den Boer & Pyo, 2011). Foot and mobile patrols are among the most effective anti-crime operations that are used by HRBP police agencies. Patrols significantly deter crimes due to the active presence of uniformed police officers. However, it is important in HRBP that police on patrols should:

- Wear proper police uniform and equipment.
- Use of properly marked vehicles.
- Always be respectful or courteous when speaking to citizens.

➤ *Problem Orientation Policing*

Problem-Oriented Policing (POP) places more emphasis on "understanding the connections between problems and why they are occurring, tackling problems identified by local communities that have been resistant to other, more conventional responses" (Longstaff, Willer, Chapman, Czarnomski & Graham, 2015:25-26). The POP model requires a thorough analysis of the causes of crime and disorder, identifying strategies for intervention (beyond law enforcement) and involving other agencies and the community in addressing the causes of crime (Longstaff, Willer, Chapman, Czarnomski & Graham, 2015: 26).

Police use the analytical technique known as "problem-oriented policing" (POP) to create crime-prevention and -reduction plans. According to the POP model, police departments are required to systematically analyze neighborhood issues, look for find practical answers, and evaluate their progress. (National Research Council 2004). POP stands for police-led efforts to change the environment at crime hotspots that sustain ongoing criminal problems. Law enforcement must also look into alternatives to their present strategies for dealing with crime and disorder (Weisburd and Eck 2004). It is one of the strategies that is most frequently employed today among progressive law enforcement agencies. (Weisburd et al. 2010). Herman Goldstein (1979) was the person who first proposed the POP approach, arguing that the traditional model of policing, which is primarily reactive and incident driven, should be replaced with a more proactive approach to identifying and tackling issues that fuel crime, disorder, and other community issues. The SARA (for Scanning, Analysis, Response, and Assessment) model, which was subsequently developed by Eck and Spelman (1987). One of the many possible approaches to putting POP into effect is SARA. The particular issues being addressed will determine the various forms that POP interventions can take. The SARA model, a four-step procedure, is one of the most widely used approaches for putting POP into effect.

Police use a variety of sources to identify and rank potential issues related to crime and disorder in an area during the first stage, scanning. This can involve identifying issues that the community is concerned about, verifying their existence, determining their effects, and working out how frequently they occur. Analysis comes next after the issue has been located. In order to learn more about the issue, including possibly reducing its scope and finding potential causes, this step of the process entails locating and analyzing pertinent data. The choice of the most appropriate and effective solution to the issue is made using this knowledge in the subsequent step. Response, police, and their partners choose one or more responses or interventions in the third stage based on the findings of the analysis carried out in the previous step. The nature of each response, the precise goals it is meant to accomplish, and the roles of

the different partners involved in its implementation are all listed in a response plan. The police and their partners execute the chosen response once it has been decided upon. The final stage in the assessment process is to determine whether the responses were carried out in accordance with the response plan and whether they had the desired effects. Thus, both components of the process evaluation and the impact evaluation are included in the assessment step.

Different POP strategies can be used. Strategies may target geographically concentrated crime and other issues, such as serial offenders, victims, and times, or they may target non-geographic concentrations of crime and other issues. POP's key components include choosing a problem type with a specific focus and implementing a broad range of targeted solutions meant to lessen the frequency or severity of that problem type. The involvement of partners outside the police agency and the importance of data and information in choosing a problem type, analyzing it, evaluating the answers, and making adjustments as necessary are additional crucial components. POP mainly depends on a variety of narrowly focused policing strategies, some of which use conventional law enforcement techniques and others which use alternative techniques. POP shares some similarities with other new advancements in policing, such as third-party policing, focused deterrence, and hot spots policing. The core components of POP are unique, though.

Hot spots policing's resource-targeting tactics and the various community policing methods are combined in problem-oriented policing. In order to address problems of crime and disorder, community policing uses a variety of strategies, including collaborations between the police and other organizations and neighborhood groups. Community policing, on the other hand, does not always entail the same level of intense concentration on a particular problem type as POP. The use of third parties to help the police address issues in the community is known as third-party enforcement. The majority of hot spots policing tactics use conventional law enforcement techniques. However, police authority and resources are focused on addressing a particular crime-ridden region or offending population (National Research Council 2004, 249). Last but not least, focused deterrence strategies frequently draw significantly on problem-oriented policing techniques, but they also have a number of unique characteristics that go beyond the most common definitions of POP. Weisburd and Eck provide a visual depiction of the relationship between the POP approach's diversity and its level of focus in comparison to other policing tactics like community-oriented and hot spots policing (2004: 45).

➤ *Objectives of Problem-Oriented Policing*

The objective of POP model is to ensure a reduction in crime and disorder by ensuring that problems that are recurring and connected are identified and immediate responses are established through collaborations (Longstaff, Willer, Chapman, Czarnomski & Graham, 2015: 26). POP also intends to eradicate problems in society and remove the burden of responsibility on the police and making social

control the responsibility of all people in society such as the community, other government agencies, private sector, etc (Den Boer & Pyo, 2011: 22).

➤ *Characteristics of Problem-Oriented Policing*

POP is characterised by its nature of focusing on the identification and examination of problems to develop effective responses that are rigorously evaluated. This initiative is achieved through the Scanning, Analysis, Response and the Assessment (SARA) model (Office of Community Oriented Policing Services, United States, 2010:6) which is described in detail below:

- **Scanning** refers to identification of community and organizational concerns.
- **Analysis** refers to investigation of priority problems, e.g. exploring in depth what, where, when, who, how and why the problem is happening.
- **Response** refers to development of tailored, evidence-based interventions to address the problems identified and their causes.

➤ *Methods of Problem-Oriented Policing*

Methods of POP include (Den Boer & Pyo, 2011: 22):

- **Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design:** This initiative focuses on improving environments to ensure effective crime prevention or reduction and includes installing street lightings in those dark places to disrupt crime opportunities.
- **Community Mobilisation:** Community mobilisation is the process of changing community attitudes and behaviours and encouraging them to actively get involved in working with the police and include campaigning in communities to raise awareness of certain processes, procedures or responsibilities.
- **Targeted Enforcement Efforts:** This speaks to police patrols that are aimed at increasing police presence, disrupting criminal behaviour and ensuring easy police access.
- **Enforcement of Minor Violations:** This initiative encourages for taking seriously, even those crimes that are regarded to be minor e.g. violation of city/location ordinances (dumping in no-dumping areas).
- **Neighbourhood Clean-Ups:** involves efforts taken by jointly with community members to remove those signs in communities that causes fear of crime and promote opportunities for crime e.g. removing youths that are hang around in groups on the streets.
- **Use of Private Providers:** this involves the use of the private sector to assist with resources and establishment of certain programs e.g. counselling programs for victims and shelters for the needy.
- **Establishment of a Database:** to identify and track individuals causing repeat problem.
- **Undercover Operations:** use of undercover operations to gather important information that is needed in the process of investing a crime, arresting and prosecuting offenders.

- *Use of the Media:* the media is used to ensure progress in order to ensure positive light in areas and also to highlight the existence of certain problems that needs to be addressed.
- *Tenant Screening:* tenant screening involves the establishment of methods for screening those potential problem tenants in communities.
- *Conveying Information:* this entails spreading awareness across all stakeholders who are affected by the problem.
- *Use of Social Services Agencies:* this is intended to address those underlying root causes of crime and involves collaborative efforts across all government agencies.
- *Assessment* refers to evaluation of the implementation and outcome achieved on tailored and evidence-based interventions.

➤ *Predictive Policing Model*

Hooper (2013:103) defines Predictive Policing as a, “strategy that develops and uses information and advanced analysis to inform forward-thinking crime prevention.” The idea is for the police to use existing information to provide awareness about certain situations in society and to anticipate intervention or responses which could work best in such situations (Perry, McInnis, Price, Smith & Hollywood, 2012: 4).

➤ *Methods of Predictive Policing*

Perry et al (2013: 4) highlight the following analytical techniques which can be employed in predictive policing:

- *Hot Spot Analysis:* Police officers identify areas with high crime rates and focus intervention on them.
- *Near Repeat Methods:* This method is based on the theory that when an area experiences crime, the chances are it will occur again in the future. Therefore, police concentrate on the areas that have experienced high crime rates to prevent future occurrences.
- *Risk Terrain Modelling:* This entails the identification of high crime locations to assess nearby locations which might also be at risk of also experiencing crime.
- *Regression And Data Mining:* This entails the use of crime history and other factors such a demographics to estimate future crime.

The advantage of this policing model is the utilisation of limited resources to prevent and respond to crime. Nonetheless, the model is not always effective because police responses and operations are informed by predictions which might not always be accurate (Perry et al., 2013: 23; 33).

VIII. CONCLUSION

A number of models were found, and the vast majority of them fit under the umbrella category of community policing. This includes some forms of problem-focused, neighborhood-focused, citizen-focused, and reassurance-focused policing. Community-oriented policing, problem-oriented policing, and neighborhood policing approaches were all correctly categorized under the community policing

paradigm by Hunter, Barker, and Mayhall (2004). Following a thorough review of the literature on citizen-focused policing, with a focus on its definition (Home Office in Longstaff, Willer, Chapman, Czarnomski & Graham, 2015: 15, Home Office in Fisher & Kirby, 2014: 2), the methods police use to learn about the community's concerns and expectations (Den Boer & Pyo, 2011: 24), the benefits of the "model" (Llyod & Foster in Zagrodzki & It is appropriate to draw the conclusion that community policing also encompasses citizen-focused policing, as stated in Zagrodzki and ztaş (2015: 7).

The objectives listed above are sufficient to justify the inclusion of reassurance policing under the ambit of community policing. In view of the above, community policing, throughout this document, shall be defined as an, “overarching concept for community-oriented policing, problem-oriented policing, neighbourhood policing, citizen-focused policing and reassurance policing.” Based on the literature that was studied, the researchers are convinced that community policing is “the model”, while the rest are just variations. Before providing reasons for placing community-oriented policing, problem-oriented policing, neighbourhood policing, citizen-focused policing and reassurance policing, under community policing, it is essential to define these concepts.

Okeshola and Mudiare (2013: 134) define community-oriented policing as a, “proactive philosophy that promotes solving problems that are either criminal, affect the quality of life, or increase citizens fear of crime. It involves identifying, analysing and addressing community problems at their source. Strategies employed in community policing include community partnership, problem solving and change management.”

Goldstein (2001) defines problem-oriented policing as, “an approach to policing in which discrete pieces of police business (each consisting of a cluster of similar incidents, whether crime or acts of disorders, which the police are expected to handle) are subject to microscopic examination (drawing on the especially honed skills of crime analysts and the accumulated experience of operating field personnel) in hopes that what is freshly learned about a problem will lead to discovering a new and more effective strategy for dealing with it.” Although the above definition makes no mention of community involvement in problem identification and solving, researches still find it necessary to include problem-oriented policing as one of the variations of community policing because there is no way one can able to identify a problem in the community without involving the community. Policing paradigms are not exclusive of one another. The majority of the police model research is complementary. Some of the models employ principles that are similar yet have distinct names in other languages. The country will suffer if one particular model is adopted as "the model" for the police, in light of this insight.

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